

CREDITING - AN ESSENTIAL ADAPTIVE ELEMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ROMANIAN ECONOMY OVER TIME

Sorin Adrian TOADER ¹, Dana Elena Morar ²,
PhD Student ¹, Lecturer ²
Technical University of Cluj-Napoca
Cluj-Napoca, Memorandumului St., No. 28, Romania
sorinadrian.toader@gmail.com ¹, dana.morar@ccm.utcluj.ro ²
<http://www.utcluj.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – *The primary objective of this paper is to foster a deeper comprehension of the historical events and legal frameworks that have shaped the evolution of the credit system in this country. Additionally, beyond providing a thought-provoking theme, this study aims to offer a valuable resource for understanding the past and making informed business decisions today. By examining the credit market's history, contemporary strategists and decision-makers can better navigate the complexities of the ever-changing business landscape. This research endeavors to shed light on the credit market's significance in Romania's economic development, highlighting intrinsically the challenges and opportunities that await it in the future.*

Methodology / Approach – *By examining the context, economic conditions, and legal regulations, this study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the credit market's evolution and its impact on Romania's overall economic development. The analysis traces the credit market's trajectory from the early 19th century to the end of the Second World War, enlightening the key milestones, challenges, and opportunities that have shaped its course. Moreover, the paper delves into the legal and regulatory frameworks that have governed the credit market over time. By analyzing the evolution of credit laws, regulations, and institutions, the study clarifies some of the factors that have shaped the credit market's structure, functioning, and accessibility.*

Findings – *Through the study of the past and applying its insights, organizations can enhance their ability to navigate uncertainty, adapt to change, and position themselves for long-term growth and prosperity.*

Research Limitations / Implications – *Although, the findings in this paper can have practical and theoretical implications for the organizations which try to improve continuously their adaptability and navigate the challenges of today's dynamic business scene, the focus of this survey is centered upon a specific aspect of the financial area, respectively the credit evolution, while in the business environment, challenges can appear from many, different directions.*

Originality / Value – *By combining historical analysis, economic theory, legal frameworks, and demographic data, consulting the works of renowned scholars in the fields of economics, history, and law, we endeavored to provide a deeper understanding of the complex interplay between historical events, economic conditions, and legal regulations in shaping the development of the credit system in this country.*

Key words: *Credit market, credit evolution, financial legislation*

Introduction

Romania's credit market has evolved through a complicated interplay of history, economics, and law. By understanding the historical context, identifying key trends, and applying the lessons learned from the credit market, present-day organizations can enhance their resilience, improve their ability to navigate uncertainty, and position themselves for long-term success.

The Credit Market in the Main Romanian Provinces: Wallachia, Moldavia, and Transylvania until the Great Union of 1918

In the mid-19th century, the three provinces were once again separate and under the domination of foreign powers. Since Wallachia and Moldavia were under Ottoman rule, while Transylvania was part of the Habsburg Empire, this subject will be approached collectively for the first two provinces and separately for Transylvania, up until 1918, the year of the Great Union.

The Credit Market in the Romanian Provinces of Wallachia and Moldavia until the Unification of 1859

Before the Unification of 1859 under the leadership of Alexandru Ioan Cuza, the two Romanian provinces, Wallachia and Moldavia, which were under Ottoman domination, were economically underdeveloped compared to Western countries. Among the causes of this situation were foreign domination, the semi-isolation of the Southeast European space from Western economic flows, frequent wars fought on their territory, the existence of a Balkan mentality that supported corruption, weak institutional structuring, and long periods of instability.

In this context, the ongoing corruption within the administration, excessive, discretionary, and chaotic taxation, and the venality of the ruling class and officials severely affected the spirit of accumulation and saving, as well as trust in honest work, institutions in general, and the political elite in particular. Thus, against the backdrop of maintaining Ottoman domination, medieval forms of economy persisted, delaying political division and the formation of a national economic market. Additionally, the monetary situation was chaotic, with money regarded as a commodity like all other goods. There was no national currency, and a multitude of foreign currency signs circulated, with over 80 varieties in use (BNR, 2005). This monetary system was exposed to significant external and internal speculation and fluctuations, varying from day to day and from one locality to another, which undermined the function of value measurement. To this, one could add the intentional deterioration of coins to extract precious metal, as well as the practice of hoarding.

As shown in Table 1, during this period, a usury credit system operated, consisting of "large" and "small" loans. The former were intended for the wealthy clientele, nobility, large merchants, and the state, and were practiced by loan sharks, money changers, and large merchants. The debts of these beneficiaries became perpetual, with debtors being constantly indebted. Nevertheless, the risks were relatively low due to solid guarantees, usually real estate such as estates and buildings. It is noted that this type of credit was unproductive, as it was intended for covering luxury expenses, such as travel and stays abroad (Axenciuc, 1997).

In parallel, "small" loans were available to peasants, craftsmen, small merchants, and various employees, practiced by landowners, tenants, innkeepers, and specialized small loan sharks. Interest rates for these loans reached up to 200 percent, a level reflecting not only the pressure of demand but also higher risks due to the lack of guarantees. This type of credit was unproductive, as interest rates were generally higher than average profit rates, reducing the beneficiaries' chances of achieving a better standard of living. During that time, Romanian

society was marked by the urgency of modernizing internal institutions and strengthening national construction.

Table 1: The Usury Lending System in Wallachia and Moldavia in the Mid-19th Century

Type of Credit	Beneficiaries	Providers	Characteristics	Risks	Guarantees
Large	Wealthy clientele, nobility, large merchants, state	Loan sharks, money changers, large merchants	Non-productive; intended for luxury expenses (travel, stays abroad)	Low	Real estate - estates, houses, land
Small	Farmers, craftsmen, small merchants, employees	Landowners, tenants, innkeepers, small specialized loan sharks	Unproductive: interest rates are generally higher than average profit rates	High	No guarantees

The Credit Market in the United Principalities from the Unification of 1859 to the Great Union of 1918

With the establishment of the modern Romanian national state in 1859, accomplished under the leadership of Alexandru Ioan Cuza, alongside political changes, there was also a transition from the pre-modern feudal system to a modern market economy. During this period, there was a pressing need for low-interest loans; large landowners, the bourgeoisie, and individuals with more modest resources felt the absence of a banking system, particularly an issuing bank, which would have allowed them to move away from ruinous usurious loans. The increased accessibility of credit was crucial for the success of their enterprises.

The situation was addressed through the adoption of important laws and the creation, over the course of a decade, of several institutions responsible for lending, such as the House of Deposits and Consignments (December 1, 1864), Rural Land Credit (June 1, 1873), and Urban Land Credit (Bucharest Urban Credit Society) (1875) (Giurescu, 2007). The emergence of these institutions was a reflection of a new business spirit based on credit and cultivated public confidence in domestic financial power.

An important innovation during this period, which prepared significant changes in the credit market, was the introduction of a national monetary system based on the Law of April 22 / May 4, 1867.

As a result of the adoption of the new monetary system, the first real national currency with intrinsic value, the Leu, was created, expressed in precious metal, despite Ottoman resistance and Austro-Hungarian protests. One leu was equivalent to 0.3226 grams of gold with a fineness of 900 per thousand or five grams of silver with a fineness of 835 per thousand. The leu was defined according to the decimal and bimetallic system of the Latin Monetary Union, which included France, Belgium, Switzerland, Italy, and Luxembourg (BNR, 2005).

The monetary stability characteristic of the gold standard system during the period 1880-1914 resulted in remarkable price stability, which was unprecedented for the next 110 years. Thus, Romania entered the international trade and currency exchange market with a stable and efficient monetary organization (Kirițescu & Dobrescu, 1998).

Table 2: Leu Exchange Rates – Common Currencies in the Period 1880 – 1914

Exchange Rates	1 real (Spain)	1\$ (USA)	1 £ (GB)	1 RM Reichsmark (Germany)
Lei	5.039	5.18	25.25	1.24

At the same time, in the United Principalities, which were named Romania after 1877, the year of independence from Ottoman domination, following the adoption of the Law for the issuance of mortgage bonds in the amount of 30 million lei (June 12, 1877), backed and guaranteed by state lands, paper money began to circulate for the first time. This marked a significant step forward in the evolution of the national monetary system.

The establishment of a national banking system was marked by the founding of the National Bank of Romania through the Law for the establishment of a discount and circulation bank dated April 17/29, 1880, published in the Official Gazette no. 90, in the form of a joint-stock company, with a share capital of 30,000,000 lei, one-third subscribed by the Romanian state and two-thirds by private investors.

As a result of these changes, a modern credit system for large investments was implemented, characterized by an abundance relative to demand, interest rates lower than the average profit rate, and a specialization in the main branches of the economy such as trade, industry, and agriculture. It had a predominantly productive nature, being intended for investments and economic transactions. Additionally, the system was based on reasonable guarantees, making it stimulative for deposits.

Among the economic progress recorded as a result of the new system, the number of enterprises increased to 175 by 1877, the expansion of the petroleum and salt extraction industries, the development and modernization of transportation routes, the increase in the number of imported agricultural machines, and the use of wage labor in agriculture were notable. The number of traders also increased, and foreign trade doubled between 1864 and 1880. Of the total exports, 85 percent was represented by wheat, which earned Romania the title of the "granary of Europe" (BNR, 2005).

Tables 3, 4, and 5 present the types of specialized loans from this period, several important banking institutions, and the sources of capital. It is primarily noted that credit supports activities in agriculture, the main concern of the population. Regarding capital, there is a good representation of both banks with domestic capital and those with Austrian, German, French, and English capital, many of which were supported by representatives of the Jewish minority (Boelcke, 1987).

Table 3: Types of Loans Offered by Specialized Banks

Year	Types of Credit	Banking Institution
1880	Issuing bank and main credit institution	National Bank of Romania
1873	Agricultural Credit	First Land Credit Society
1874	Land Credit	Bucharest Urban Land Credit Society
1881	Land Credit	Iași Urban Land Credit Society
1903	Credit for Small Farmers	Popular Banks
1906	Credit for Vine Growers	Wine Credit House
1906	Credit for Urban Areas	Urbanization Credit House
1908	Credit for Rural Areas	Rural Credit House

Table 4: Banks with Foreign Capital

Source of Capital	Year of Establishment	Banking Institution
German capital	1895	Romanian General Bank
Austrian capital	1904	Romanian Credit Bank
Jewish bank with Hungarian, German, and French capital	1905	Marmorosch – Blank Bank
English, Austrian, French, and Belgian capital	1906	Romanian Commercial Bank

Table 5: Banks with Romanian Capital

Banking Institution	Year of Establishment
House of Deposits and Consignments	1864
House of Savings and Postal Checks	1880
Agricultural Bank	1894
Discount Bank of Bucharest	1898
Commerce Bank of Craiova	1898
Romanian Bank (PNL)	1910

This period manages to bring modernization and essential changes to the credit market, the main evolution being the transition from the suffocating usury credit system to a sustainable lending system practiced by the new banking institutions.

The Credit Market in Transylvania between the Mid-19th Century and the Great Union of 1918

Between the mid-19th century and the Great Union of 1918, Transylvania was under Habsburg domination. In this province, alongside the majority Romanian population (61.3 percent), there were also smaller proportions of Hungarian, German, and Jewish minorities (see Table 6) (Cosma, 1880). Paradoxically, the Romanians in Transylvania were the only ones bound to the land, as serfdom was only abolished in 1853. The former serfs, now free peasants, lacked organized credit for agriculture, as lending was based on ethnicity. As shown in Table 8, the first Romanian bank, Albina, was established in Sibiu in 1871, designed to offer loans to the Romanian population, with the aim of ensuring financial resources for the exploitation of local resources. It became the most important Romanian credit institution in Transylvania (Giurescu, 2007). At the same time, the other nationalities, accounting for less than 40 percent, benefited from 16 strong credit institutions, branches of banks from Vienna and Budapest.

Land sales and usurious loans became widespread during this period, driven by "heavy and burdensome debts", (Retegan, 1994) both for survival and for paying taxes to the state, as the treasury was no longer willing to accept arrears (Balog, 2007).

The population of Transylvania in 1850 was 2,061,645 inhabitants, the vast majority being Romanians (see Table 6).

Table 6: Population and Banks in Transylvania

Population by Ethnicity*	Percentage of Total Population*	Number of Credit Institutions	Name of Institutions	Purpose of the Loan	Accepted Guarantees
Romanians	61.3%	1	Albina Bank (1871)	Land, livestock, agricultural machinery and tools, building constructions, payment of debts, trade, promoting crafts, children's education, passions and gambling, for productive and non-productive things	Real estate and agricultural land
Hungarians	19.4%	16	Branches of Banks from Vienna and Budapest in Arad, Sibiu, Braşov, Cluj, Timișoara		
Germans	11.9%				
Jews	3.4%				
Others	4%				

*Source: (Rotariu, Semeniuc, & Mezei, 2004)

During this period, the lack of strong banks serving the Romanian population, both for financing agriculture and industry, reduced their chances of prosperity. Although the Furnica Bank was established in 1883 and the Ardeleana Bank in 1885, usury as a lending method continued to play an important role. The lack of education and poor preparation of the Romanian population led to excessive indebtedness of small landholdings, resulting in an increasing number of properties being sold at auction. The number of small properties sold at auction rose alarmingly by the end of the 19th century, from 9,606 properties in 1875 to 14,921 in 1893, reaching 21,193 in 1903.

Through the information provided, the publications *Gazeta Transilvaniei* and *Revista Economică* played a very important role in improving the economic situation in Transylvania, even though, at times, the authors of the articles did not succeed in making accurate predictions regarding solutions for the development of Romanian agriculture and industry (Dobrescu, 1999).

The Credit System from the Great Union to the End of the Second World War 1918-1945

After World War I and the formation of Greater Romania, the banking system experienced a sinusoidal evolution: between 1918 and 1929, the number of banks increased under the influence of inflation and stock market speculation from 1919 to 1926, rising from 215 in 1918 to 1,122 in 1928, in addition to the 4,743 popular banks. This was followed by a process of deterioration and contraction during the economic crisis of 1930-1934 (Căpraru, 2014).

During this period, there was a deepening of credit specialization, with the emergence of industrial loans, craft loans, and loans for public servants. Large banks oriented themselves towards mechanized industry and foreign trade, while small banks targeted domestic trade and small to medium agriculture; most of the loans were directed, especially after the economic crisis, towards large industry, while agriculture had financial resources far below its needs.

In the third decade (1921-1930), the positions held by French, Italian, Swiss, and British banking capital were consolidated by the displacement of German capital, and during the period of 1934-1938, a trend for the revitalization of German capital became evident. At the same time, trends of concentration and centralization of banking capital became apparent, with most assets held by a few large banks centered around the National Bank of Romania (BNR).

In the fourth decade (1931-1940), state intervention became necessary in the form of regulatory and control actions over banking activities, as a result of the disorganization caused by the banking crisis and the collapse of many credit institutions.

The Composition of the Credit System during the Interwar Period

During the interwar period, the credit system included the National Bank of Romania as the sole issuing bank and central discount bank, private commercial banks, specialized credit institutions in the fields of large and small industries, agriculture, employee credit institutions, cooperative credit institutions, public credit institutions, and insurance institutions.

As a consequence of the economic crisis in the fourth decade of the 20th century, Law No. 70 of May 8, 1934, was enacted for the organization and regulation of banking commerce, establishing the High Banking Council, whose leadership was appointed by the National Bank of Romania (BNR). This body had the functions of removing weak banks from the banking network by either closing or merging them; a series of restrictions were introduced to bring order to banking operations; speculative businesses were halted, with the goal of restoring and consolidating the banking system.

Period		Phenomenon	Manifestations
1921	1930	Deepening of credit specialization	Industrial, craft, and public servant credit
			Large banks support large industry and foreign trade
			Small banks support domestic trade and small to medium agriculture
		French, Italian, and Swiss banking capital predominates	
1934	1938	Trends of concentration and centralization of banking capital (revival of German capital)	The majority of assets were held by a few large banks, centered around the National Bank of Romania (BNR)
1930	1940	Banking crisis	Collapse of many credit institutions

Figure 1: Synthesis of Banking Phenomena during the Interwar Period

A special case is represented by the Credit Cooperatives, initially established as Popular Credit Associations. In 1870, the "Economy" Association was founded in Bucharest at the initiative of His Eminence Aurelian, followed by the establishment of credit cooperatives in the counties of Dâmbovița, Buzău, Neamț, Prahova, and Roman. In 1846, the "Sick Benefit, Burial, and Travel Assistance Association of Printers from Brașov" was established in Brașov, the first mutual aid association in Brașov, whose statutes were approved in 1861. A similar association was established in Timișoara in 1851. In 1868, the "Society for Saving and Lending in Rășinari" (Sibiu County) was founded, which was the first Romanian credit institution in Transylvania aimed at harnessing the economic potential of the villages (Giurescu, 2007).

Through the amendments made to the law on June 23, 1938, January 20, 1939, October 18, 1940, and February 22, 1941, the National Institute of Cooperation (INCOOP) was established, which abolished the five previous centers, with the state becoming a partner alongside federations and cooperatives.

Conclusions

From the above, it follows that throughout the history Romania faced a multitude of challenges, but its resilience and adaptation to changing circumstances have paved the way for a more robust and integrated financial sector. As Romania continues its journey toward economic development, the credit market will undoubtedly play a pivotal role in driving growth and prosperity, particularly for those organizations that possess a deeper understanding of the historical context, can identify emerging trends, and apply the lessons of the past, some of them learned from the evolution of the credit system.

References

Axenciuc, V.

1997

Introducere în istoria economică a României: epoca modernă. București: Editura Fundației "România de Măine".

Balog, I. M.

2007

Dilemele Modernizării. Cluj-Napoca: International Book Access.

BNR, B. N.

2005

"BNR Istorie Începuturile". Retrieved from Banca Națională a României: <https://www.bnr.ro/Inceputurile--1053-Mobile.aspx>

Boelcke, W. A.

1987

Wirtschafts- und Sozialgeschichte. Einführung, Bibliographie, Methoden, Problemfelder. Darmstadt: Wissenschaftliche Buchgesellschaft.

Căpraru, B.

2014

Activitatea bancară. Sisteme, operațiuni și practici. Ediția 2. București: C.H. Beck.

Cosma, P.

1880

Datele referitoare la regularea de posesiune în Transilvania și părțile anexe. Sibiu: Jurnalul.

Dobrescu, V.

1999

Sistemul românesc de credit din Transilvania 1867-1918. Tg. Mureș: Editura Universității Petru Maior.

Giurescu, D. C.

2007

History of Romania in Dates, 2nd Edition. Bucharest: Encyclopedic Publishing House.

Kirițescu, C. C., & Dobrescu, E. M.

1998

Moneda – Mică enciclopedie. București: Editura Enciclopedică.

Retegan, S.

1994, May

"Tranzacții funciare în comitatul Solnocul Inferior la mijlocul secolului al XIX-lea". In Cele Trei Crișuri, pp. 8-12.

Rotariu, T. C., Semeniuc, M., & Mezei, E.

2004

Recensământul din 1850, Transilvania. Ed A II-a revazută. Cluj-Napoca: Presa Universitară Clujeană.